

**PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MENTALLY WEAK
ADOLESCENTS WITH ATTENTION DEFICIT HYPERACTIVITY
DISORDERS**

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Annotation

The article provides general information about hyperactivity and its symptoms, the causes and specific features of hyperactivity, as well as hyperactivity in young children. It covers the causes of attention deficit in hyperactive children, the research of R. Barkley, L. Adler, J. Biederman, P. Altcher on ADHD. ADHD is characterized by increased motor activity, impaired attention, excessive fatigue and impulsivity.

Keywords: attention deficit, hyperactivity, ADHD, impulsivity, personality traits, accentuation, aggression, socialization.

INTRODUCTION

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is one of the most important psychological problems facing modern schools. According to statistics, its prevalence in the child population ranges from 2–20%. This disorder is characterized by increased motor activity, impaired attention, excessive fatigue, and impulsivity.

Children with ADHD cannot concentrate on an activity for a long time, which creates difficulties in mastering the curriculum and leads to impaired social adaptation. Most studies have focused on normally developing children, and ADHD in children with mental retardation has been poorly studied.

In recent years, the concept of comorbid disorders - the simultaneous manifestation of several mental disorders - has become widespread. The combination of mental retardation and ADHD has a significant impact on the formation of the adolescent's personality, but this issue has not been sufficiently studied.

The situation is not accidental and is clearly associated with a number of factors, among which the following can be distinguished:

- The complexity and ambiguity of understanding ADHD;
- The influence of the concept that low intelligence excludes ADHD.

However, the last decades of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century have brought about changes in the mental development of children and deviations in this development, which inevitably led to a revision of many positions in childhood psychopathology. Thus, recently, the concept of comorbid disorders in diagnostics has become widespread - a two- or multi-layered structure of mental disorders. This concept involves the identification of not only symptoms that are "on the surface", but also disorders that are not so obvious and nevertheless affect the diagnosed disease. ADHD in children and adolescents with intellectual disabilities is an example of comorbid mental disorders. However, the relationship between ADHD and mental retardation, and their overall impact on the formation of a child's personality, is still not well understood. Hypothesis: in adolescents with mental retardation and ADHD comorbidity, the socialization process is complicated and personality development is impaired.

METHODS

Applied methods:

- Biographical method
- Observation
- Interview with parents

Experimental techniques:

- Bass–Darky aggression test
- Schmishek personality accentuation test
- Personal anxiety test (Tammle–Dorkey–Amenda)
- Luscher color test
- Relationship color test
- Dembo–Rubinstein self-assessment method

RESULTS

The study revealed the following:

- Anxiety, aggression, personality accentuation, and self-esteem disorders were observed in adolescents with comorbidity of ADHD and mental retardation.
- They experience difficulties in relationships with parents, teachers, and peers.
- Demonstrative and hyperthymic accentuation are manifested by a desire for social attention.
- The excitable type is characterized by impulsivity, irritability, and poor self-control.
- Self-esteem is high in some indicators, which is manifested as a compensatory mechanism.

DISCUSSION

The results confirmed that the combination of ADHD and mental retardation has a negative impact on the socialization of adolescents. This comorbid disorder leads to the formation of specific personality traits and the strengthening of destructive behavior.

Impulsivity and inattention are stronger in adolescents with ADHD and mental retardation, which form maladaptive behavior. Without special correction programs, these disorders persist.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop differential diagnostics and correction and development programs.

CONCLUSION

Comorbidity of ADHD and mental retardation has a significant impact on the personal development and socialization of adolescents. Anxiety, aggression, impulsivity, and interpersonal disorders are more common in such adolescents. Early diagnosis, psychocorrection and developmental programs are necessary for their successful integration into society.

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